

ADJECTIVE SENTENCES IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

The article addresses a controversial issue in linguistics regarding the status and existence of noun-phrase one-member sentences with an adjective as the principal member in modern English. The author analyzes traditional approaches in Soviet and foreign English philology, which conventionally classified syntactic constructions like *Beautiful!* or *Impossible* as elliptical (incomplete) two-member sentences. This paper argues for the semantic, stylistic, and communicative independence of adjectival one-member sentences. Based on functional analysis, the study demonstrates their structural divergence from incomplete sentences, outlines their specific roles in declarative discourse, and accounts for the systematic absence of such structures in interrogative and imperative modalities.

Keywords

one-member sentence, adjectival clause, noun-phrase sentence, principal member, incomplete sentence, two-member structure.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается дискуссионный в лингвистике вопрос о наличии и статусе номинативных (именных) односоставных предложений (ОП) с прилагательным в роли главного члена в современном английском языке. Автор анализирует традиционные подходы советской и зарубежной англистики, в которых синтаксические конструкции типа *Beautiful!* или *Impossible* классифицировались как эллиптические (неполные) двусоставные предложения. В работе доказывается семантическая, стилистическая и коммуникативная самостоятельность адъективных ОП. На основе функционального анализа обосновывается их отличие от неполных структур, выявляются особенности их функционирования в повествовательном дискурсе, а также объясняются

причины отсутствия данных конструкций в вопросительной и побудительной модальностях.

Ключевые слова: односоставное предложение, адъективное предложение, именное предложение, главный член предложения, неполное предложение, двусоставная структура.

The question of whether noun-phrase one-member sentences with an adjective as the principal clause member exist in English was barely addressed in Soviet English philology. In N.S. Bukhtiyarova's dissertation[1], as well as in all traditional grammar[2], sentences such as *Unbelievable* and *Impossible* are treated as incomplete, acting as syntactic synonyms for sentences like *It is Impossible* (Это невозможное).

Thus, adjectival clauses with a qualitative-evaluative meaning were generally considered incomplete two-member sentences in which the formal subject and the linking verb are omitted. This is apparently explained not only by the fact that the study of the one-member sentence as an independent structural type in English is influenced by and dependent on the traditional view—which recognizes only two-member sentences as the norm and model, thereby either excluding any deviations from the two-member pattern from the category of sentences altogether or classifying them as two-member sentences with certain omitted members—but also by the fact that the line between one-member and incomplete sentences does indeed prove to be unstable and blurred in a number of cases.

The analyzed one-member sentences were most frequently declared incomplete, with an omission of the subject and linking verb that can be mentally inferred or supplied from the sentence context itself[3].

However, sentences like *Beautiful!* and others are complete in meaning, providing a qualitative-evaluative description of an event, object, action, etc., mentioned in the preceding sentence. Such sentences, therefore, are not perceived as semantically incomplete; thus, there is not only no need to mentally infer or restore supposedly missing members, but doing so—driven by a desire to match these sentences with their functional-syntactic two-member synonym of the *It is beautiful!*

type—to some extent alters the stylistic and semantic nuance of the sentence, as well as the uniqueness of its emotional character.

Nevertheless, it must be admitted that this issue remains controversial, as the boundaries between incomplete sentences and one-member sentences with an adjective as the principal member are not always distinct.

Differentiating one-member sentences from incomplete ones is also complicated by the fact that a clear criterion for sentence incompleteness in English has not yet been developed.

Declarative one-member sentences, whose principal member is expressed by an adjective, are typically used to express a qualitative-evaluative characteristic and attitude toward what was stated in the previous sentence: *Marvelous!* (Чудесно!); *Excellent!* (Отлично!); *Great!* (Здорово!).

The structure of such sentences is simple. Most often they are unextended (bare), since the lexical meaning of the adjective used as the principal member possesses a sufficiently vivid evaluative quality. Sometimes the principal member can be extended by an adverbial modifier: *Very reasonable!* (Очень разумно!); *Absolutely correct!* (Абсолютно верно!).

The principal member of such one-member sentences expresses the predicate of a judgment that correlates with an impersonal subject, since the subject here is not a specific person or object, but the entire situation being evaluated.

A distinct structural and stylistic variety of the adjectival clause consists of sentences in which the principal member proper is preceded by the adverb *how*: *How delightful!* *How romantic!* (Как восхитительно! Как романтично!); *How very odd!* (Как очень странно!); *How severe of you!* (Как строго с твоей стороны!).

It should be emphasized that the sentences cited above fundamentally differ from incomplete two-member sentences. Their syntactic completeness requires no additional members: any attempt to supply or, conversely, exclude anything would lead to the destruction of their structural specificity, as well as to the loss of their inherent semantic and stylistic nuances. These sentences function as independent syntactic units possessing their own communicative value.

In English, interrogative one-member sentences with an adjective in the principal member position do not exist, which is explained both by the grammatical limitations of the language (the insufficient independence of the adjective in the predicative function) and by the specifics of the communicative organization of English speech, where interrogative forms are predominantly realized within the framework of two-member sentences.

Imperative sentences whose principal member is expressed by an adjective do not exist, since the meaning of inducement is incompatible with the concept of a quality or property of an object.

Thus, the English language is characterized by the presence of noun-phrase one-member sentences. One-member noun-phrase sentences are used mainly to state a fact, event, etc.

The specific characteristics of the parts of speech used to form the principal members of one-member sentences are preserved—that is, they remain identical for both two-member sentences and one-member sentences.

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